

“To create more fully democratic access to knowledge across the world, we would also need to ensure that authors in other countries can not only read but also publish without having to pay.”

Page says academia needs to radically rethink how knowledge is shared and paid for to ensure equitable dissemination around the globe.

Determined that her research should be freely accessible to anyone and everyone, she always publishes open access.

She says it is both easier to achieve and less costly than people expect.

“I’ve never had to pay to publish an open access book and don’t believe I should. You aren’t limited to publishers that advertise open access routes.”

Joanna Page,
Professor of Latin
American Studies
at the University of
Cambridge, Director of
CRASSH

Page’s tips on open access publishing

Ask publishers if they publish open access (this is not always advertised)

Find out if a publisher has a waiver scheme

Some publishers run pilot initiatives

If a publisher requires a fee, check if there is a waiver scheme or another source of funds.

Funding is often available from a number of sources, e.g., institutional funds.